

VERBAL AND PHYSICAL AGGRESSION EXPERIENCED BY GRADE 6 PUPILS: BASIS FOR AN INTERVENTION PROGRAM

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Abstract: This qualitative case study aimed to analyze and interpret the verbal and physical aggression experienced by the Grade 6 learners of Tupi 1 District, Division of South Cotabato. An in-depth interview was conducted with the four (4) Grade 6 pupils aged 11-15 years old. The responses of the participants were categorized into three main themes. These were; experiences, impact and victory, and lessons. The participants had common ideas and experiences on the verbal and physical aggression they experienced. They were maladjusted, physically weaker, peer rejected and its impacts to them were anxiety, depression, loneliness as victims of verbal and physical aggression. With the support of their families and teachers, they were able to manage their stress as they learned to forgive and help others.

Keywords: educational management, verbal and physical aggression, experiences, grade 6 learners, Philippines.

1. INTRODUCTION

Due to verbal and physical aggression, victimization has become a hot topic in child psychology. According to numerous studies, being a victim of it has been linked to increased levels of internalizing distress. According to one generally used definition of verbal and physical aggressiveness, a victim may be subjected to repeated unpleasant behavior (frequency) that is deliberate and entails a power imbalance between the bully and the victim. However, only a small study has been done on victimization's conventionality and power disparity (O'Moore and Kirkham, 2021; Pekrun, 2016).

Moreover, school-based aggression is a troubling trend that has gained much attention and publicity. It is one of the socio-educational concerns that has gotten much attention in the Philippines and worldwide. Fighting, mocking, and other repetitive acts aimed at harming others are examples of aggression. Aggression, whether verbal or physical, occurs frequently. The use of peer pressure by students is considered a crucial indication of academic and social challenges during their growth that needs to be addressed (Cherry, 2020; Paquette and Underwood, 2019).

Furthermore, an overview of research on methods to avoid verbal and physical aggressiveness among elementary school pupils, both males, and females, found some promising results in primary school. However, no universal models or pre-packaged educational programs for raising student and adult awareness of the problem were discovered. In light of this, the researcher set out to create an intervention program through the use of an experimental study technique to better understand

the verbal and physical aggression experienced by Grade 6 pupils, in which the researcher and the school administration will collaborate on (Babinski & McQuade, 2019; Ettekal & Ladd, 2017).

1.1 Theoretical Lens

The study was anchored on Social-Cognitive Theory by Albert Bandura, cited by Abdullah (2019). The Social Cognitive Theory explains how aggressive behaviors are developed by describing how people learn aggression through observational learning and reinforcement. Based on the Social Cognitive Theory, children and adolescents exposed to aggression and violence experience a higher rate of violence than other children and adolescents. Also, facilitators, friends, parents, and teachers act as role models, and child behaviors are shaped by modeling their positive or negative communication skills. Social Cognitive Theory (SCT) started as the Social Learning Theory (SLT) in the 1960s by Albert Bandura. It flourished into the SCT in 1986 and submits that learning happens in a social context with a dynamic and reciprocal interaction of the person, environment, and behavior. The unique feature of SCT is the emphasis on social influence and its focus on external and internal social reinforcement. SCT considers the unique way individuals acquire and maintain behavior while also considering the social environment in which individuals perform the behavior. The theory finds a person's past experiences, which factor into whether behavioral action will occur. These past experiences influence reinforcements, expectations, and expectancies, all of which shape whether a person will engage in specific behavior and the reasons why a person engages in that behavior.

The second was the Instinct Theory of Aggression by Sigmund Freud (1927). In his earlier writings, Freud believed that all human behavior originates directly or indirectly from 'EROS,' the life instinct that helps reproduce life. In this background, aggression was considered simply a reaction to blocking libidinal impulses. Thus, it was neither an automatic nor an unavoidable part of life. But in psychoanalysis and particularly after the second world war, Freud slowly came to know the presence of two primary urges, such as Eros and Thanatos or life instinct and death instinct, instead of one instinct (Life instinct) held earlier. Thus, revising his earlier view on instincts, he wrote, "After long doubts and vacillations, we have decided to assume the existence of only two basic urges, Eros or the Life instinct and Thanatos or the Destructive instinct." Thus, with experience and analysis, Freud gradually adopted the nature of human aggression. Freud proposed a second primary instinct named the Thanatos, the force of death or destruction whose energy is directed toward the destruction or termination of life, hatred, anger, violence, and aggressive feelings, actions, dealings, and behaviors.

The third was the Frustration Aggression Hypothesis. Miller and Dollard (1944) defined frustration as "that condition when a goal response suffers interference." The frustration-aggression hypothesis is based on the psychodynamic approach. When people are frustrated, they are driven to be aggressive toward the object of their frustration, but this is frequently impossible or inappropriate, so the source of their aggression is displaced on something or someone else. Frustrating events block the individual's goal-oriented behavior, threaten his self-esteem or deprive him of the opportunity to satisfy his essential motives and immediate goals. It is considered frustrating when a situation disturbs or upsets the child or the adult. But a problem that is regarded as frustrating for one person may not be frustrating for another person. Here parental training, social class, economic status, and early childhood training for frustration tolerance play their role.

Furthermore, the learners who experienced verbal and physical aggression could have positive and negative consequences that could shape their behaviors into violence. The relevance of this study is to analyze the different cases and find ways and means to address issues and concerns by making intervention programs a solution to the problem.

1.2 Research Questions

1. How do the participants describe verbal and Physical Aggression?
2. What intervention program could be formulated out of the result of the problem?

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

The qualitative method, particularly the case study, was utilized in this research. The researcher went to the particular set of interests to gather data, know, describe, and gain insights from the experiences of the Grade 6 pupils on Verbal and Physical Aggression. The researcher used techniques for the intention of the researcher to collect data, which included

interview transcripts, field notes, audio recordings, and anything else that could convey the actual words or actions of the pupils concerned in the study.

A qualitative case study is an approach to analysis that makes it easier to analyze a phenomenon using various data sources within its context. It means that the problem is not explored by one lens but rather by several lenses that make it possible to expose and appreciate several dimensions of the phenomenon (Asha, Waasdorp, and Bradshaw, 2018; Mohajan, 2018; Paquette and Underwood, 2019).

Accordingly, the study of human interpretation of events or phenomena from actual happenings in the real world is also a case study. It is where the participants' experiences invoked in the study go deeper into their minds, defining the meaning of the experience through lengthy discussions expressed by the participants (Duke and Norton, 2017; Mohajan, 2018).

I used the case study methodology because it is an efficient method to understand human experiences, penetrating their emotions, feelings, and behaviors to gain knowledge from their experiences. It clearly showed the particular aspects of the encounter and how the subjects in the situation see them. In this research, it was a suitable tool to know the teachers' teaching effectiveness during 'modern normal education' as envisaged and discussed. A case study explains the significance of the experiences of a concept or a phenomenon for many people (Hancock, Algozzine, and Lim, 2021; Banks, 2017).

In addition, the case study examines systemic consciousness in human experiences. It included protocols that qualitative researchers should follow. The researcher created research questions that would delve deeper into the significance of individual life experiences and asked people to remember their experiences (Mohajan, 2018; Paquette and Underwood, 2019).

The investigator also obtained the data, usually through in-depth interviews with individuals who have witnessed the phenomenon being investigated. Next, horizontalization was included in the data processing, and introductory statements were derived from the transcribed interviews. These preliminary statements were translated into clusters of meanings depending on how each information falls under particular psychological and psychological messages (Egan and Todorov, 2019; Firestone, 2019).

These transformations were connected for a general overview of the textural description of what was observed and the structural description of the experience and how it was experienced. The researcher incorporated the experience here with their context. Finally, the report was written so that readers could better understand the basic framework of the information (Knox and Dynes, 2020; Magalhaes and Knox, 2021).

Qualitative analysis was used in this study to eliminate assumptions to avoid possible adverse effects of beliefs that could influence the research process, thus enhancing the quality of the research study. At all times, the researcher was careful, mindful of their viewpoints and the pre-existing views on the analysis, and must learn to set aside their own a priori awareness and ex-prior knowledge (Banks, 2017; Poling, Smith, Taylor, and Worth, 2019).

I used questions from the interview guide, checked by the panelist and the esteemed research validators and research experts.

This case study used the Main Participants Interview Method with the four (4) Grade 6 pupils who experienced Verbal and Physical Aggression. In conducting qualitative research, four participants are enough for a study with participants as stated by Creswell, 2016.

Qualitative research aimed to collect data by involving individuals interested in or influenced by the problem under review. From this viewpoint, the appropriate participants should have the capacity to objectively analyze and express their experiences, the awareness and understanding of the subject being examined, and the desire to share their thoughts (Cohen, 2016; Pellegrini, 2018).

The study's participants were the four (4) Grade 6 pupils, aged 11-15 years old, who experienced Verbal and Physical Aggression in Tupi 1 District, Division of South Cotabato.

I selected four (4) Grade pupils in the different schools in Tupi 1 District by following the selected participants of the study through purposive sampling based on pre-selected criteria relevant to the research study. Purposive sampling is a judgmental or subjective sampling; it is a non-probability sampling technique that focuses on the investigated participants (Etikan and Bala 2017; Etikan, Musa, and Alkassim 2016).

Upon the approval of the supervisors and administrations, I selected four (4) Grade 6 pupils from different schools under the Tupi 1 District. These learners experienced Verbal and Physical Aggression and were recommended by their teachers.

I wanted to get only a significant number of participants for the research with four (4) participants for the in-depth interviews because of the pandemic situation and avoid face-to-face and crowds and come up with an excellent qualitative review. It is enough to provide credible information and relevant data and results. As stipulated, researchers were advised to adopt 4-23 individuals for in-depth interviews who had encountered the same phenomenon (Creswell, 2016; Ma, 2017).

I pursued my expertise in qualitative research by entering deeply into the heart of the experience to find the meaning of a phenomenon and not how many individuals have been through it. Qualitative research uses interviews to find concrete mechanisms that participants use to organize their perceptions and make sense of their environment. These structures are often obscured and taken for granted by participants from direct observation; however, qualitative interview techniques may expose such meanings (Berkowitz, 2017; Craig and Pepler, 2019; Knox and Dynes, 2020).

A qualitative research interview is a discussion whose purpose is to gather descriptions of the life-world of the interviewee concerning the interpretation of the meaning of the described phenomena. The goal of the qualitative research interview is, therefore, to see the research topic from the perspective of the interviewee and to understand how and why they have come to this particular perspective (Banks, 2017; Perry, Ostrov, Murray-Close, Blakely-McClure, Kiefer, DeJesus-Rodriguez, and Wesolowski, 2021).

An in-depth interview was conducted with the four (4) Grade 6 pupils aged 11-15 years old who experienced verbal and physical aggression. After I prepared the interview guide questions, these questions underwent validation with the respected validators according to their expertise.

Analysis of data in this research study involved summarizing the data, collecting and presenting the results to communicate the essential features. Data were analyzed using the data reduction method, display, conclusion drawing, and verification. In the analysis of data, three steps were employed. Analysis refers to the breakdown of a whole into its test components. Data analysis is a tool used to collect raw data and turn it into valuable information for users to make decisions. Data is collected and analyzed to answer questions, test hypotheses, or disprove theories (Hancock, Algozzine, and Lim, 2021; Seo, 2021; Zhang, Katsiyannis, and Herbst, 2019).

This research used data reduction, which is the abstraction of transcription data, the elimination of non-important data, and the transformation into accessible information easily understood by many (Besag, 2018; Knox and Dynes, 2020; Rr and Ngatemi, 2020).

On the other hand, the presentation of data is the arrangement of data and displays it in the form of graphic organizers such as matrices, maps, and graphs, which will allow the viewer to draw his conclusion. The last includes revisiting what the analyzed data means and assessing their implications for the issues at hand, while verification, integrally linked to the drawing of conclusions, needs reviewing the data as many times as possible to cross-check or validate these emerging conclusions. The conceptual framework also interpreted the relevant literature on the subject in qualitative research as the drawing and verification of findings (Cherry, 2020; Swit, McMaugh, and Warburton, 2018; Villancourt and Farrell, 2021).

The researchers aim to get as close as possible to the people being analyzed while performing a qualitative analysis to minimize the distance between themselves and the participants. In explaining the case study evaluated the data by thematic analysis. In research, thematic analysis is a common form of qualitative data analysis. The thematic analysis emphasized examining and recording patterns or emergent themes within data. The thematic analysis should commence with repeated readings of the data. The next step involves data coding, defining and labeling (coding) quotations in the text related to the study objective. The third stage consists of the theme recognition process. Emerging themes are trends across data sets that are important for a phenomenon's definition and are related to specific research questions (Benbenishty, Astor, and Astor, 2016; Cohen, 2016; Taylor and Smith, 2019).

This report distinctively adopted this research analysis approach. First, I transcribed all the participants' answers, establishing relevant statements. Second, the analyzed meaningful words generated concepts and ideas to help formulate meanings from participants. Third, the acquired purposes were subjected to another research process and explicitly assigned to various ideas. Fourth, I scrutinized all relevant ideas to create the clustering of essential themes. Fifth, I then looked at

the cluster for potential emerging themes. Sixth, by category, the themes were then grouped and clustered. Finally, to illustrate all the patterns from the participants' comments, I created a convergence of statements (Espelage, Low, Polanin, and Brown, 2018; Kauffman and Landrum, 2017).

I asked the approval from the District Supervisors, Principals, and other respected validators who are research experts. They checked and validated the research questionnaires, particularly the interview guide questions.

Next, I followed all the ethical procedures required by Ramon Magsaysay Memorial Colleges. Significantly, the data must be future-proof, which meant there was consistency, privacy, and security in collecting data for the study.

Then, I went through the following steps: interviewing in-depth with the study informants and note-taking. Before conducting the in-depth interviews with the study participants, it was ensured that ethical considerations were observed correctly. Then, I employed the critical principles of ethical issues that should be considered in any research study: consent and confidentiality Bloom (Christie-Mizell, 2019; Fitzpatrick, Dulin, and Piko, 2020; Ma, 2017).

Establishing rapport is a necessary component of an interview as such before conducting an interview, a meeting was first initiated with the respondents. The details of the study were explained to make them aware and understand that privacy and confidentiality would be observed. Teachers in the different schools were identified to help reach out to the informants. After identifying these five (5) teachers, they were contacted to inform them of the purpose and venue for the interview and to personally meet them in their respective schools. With their voluntary and initial agreement, they would be asked to sign a written consent (Knox and Dynes, 2020; Ettekal and Ladd, 2017; Ma, 2017).

Furthermore, all pupils were assured that information gathered were for research purposes, and all processes undertaken during the interviews were documented correctly. An accurate and written note was done during the whole interview course to avoid misconceptions and misunderstandings. All essential documents that were gathered after the discussion would be kept and labeled for safety. The notes taken were translated and saved for retrieval. Then, these collected data were summarized in Tables. These then backed the results of in-depth interviews (Paquette and Underwood, 2019; Rigby, 2019; Verlaan and Turmel, 2020).

An in-depth interview is one approach that will undertake to gather information from the study informants. The in-depth discussion is a technique designed to elicit a vivid picture of the participant's perspective on the research topic. It is not only an approach to understanding the participant's experiences. It goes deeper into their thoughts and behavior, listening to their inner voice to explore new issues. The researcher will listen to the participants' descriptions during the interview process and then repeatedly review and study the data as they transcribe (Berkowitz, 2017; Renner, Schwab, and Boel-Studt, 2019).

Additionally, in-depth interviews should be done in the most rigorous ways to ensure reliability and validity, essential concepts in qualitative research. To do this, was to avoid concluding the interview but to base everything on factual data as described by the participants during the interview so as to remove any bias or misconceptions about the results. Next, the researcher classified themes of the phenomena for the five informants of in-depth interviews (O'Moore and Kirkham, 2021; Olweus, 2017).

For the process of in-depth interviews, the assistance of a co-teacher was enlisted for the note-taking while the researcher facilitated the discussions. During the interviews, it was observed that the respondents had difficulty expressing themselves in the appropriate words, as it was expected that the respondents were to use simple dialect to communicate more deeply about the issues and concerns and their experiences about the study. As stipulated, note-taking ensured that all information was documented thoroughly, ensuring that no important detail was missed out (Duke and Norton, 2017; Taylor and Smith, 2019; Vaillancourt and Farrell, 2021).

A face-to-face interview was the primary method for collecting data. Data were collected during our audio/video recorded interview sessions conducted onsite at the agreed place where the respondents would feel safe and comfortable. I requested friends helped me reach out to the respondents by having a preliminary meeting before the formal interview to gain their trust. The researcher provided notes and recorded using cellular phone or other techno devices available before and after each consultation (Darke, Shanks, and Broadbent, 2016; Holt and Espelage, 2017; Mohajan, 2018).

Confidentiality was observed in all sessions and with all informants, consistently addressing them by pseudonyms to conceal their real identity. The researcher prepared my open-ended research questions as indicated in the interview guide and provided different or additional questions that would help my interview continuity. It also promotes trust and openness with my respondents (Boivin, Hymel, and Bukowski, 2016; Rigby and Slee, 2019; Murray, Santos, Bertoldi, Murray, Arteché, Tovo-Rodríguez, and Cooper, 2019).

Since the learners were involved in the research study, they might hesitate to reveal and withhold some data out of fear. However, as part of the rigor of analysis and resisting the temptation to pursue this report, many precautions were used to ensure that informants calculate their confidentiality and non-disclosure, wipe out their fears and create confidence and trust. To evaluate trustworthiness or qualitative analysis, the evaluative standards used to determine the reliability and validity of quantitative research are not especially important. Alternative evaluative phraseologies such as consistency, truth value, and neutrality are favored (Babinski and McQuade, 2019; McClain, Manring, Frazer, Elledge, and Fite, 2020).

Four components were observed: integrity, conformability, transferability, and reliability, to determine the report's trustworthiness.

Via peer debriefing and member verification, reputation was built. Through a joint discussion among my co-researchers, peer debriefing was carried out, where we discussed issues related to the research and how the analysis was performed. Credibility refers to the faith in the credibility of the results strengthened by evidence supporting the evaluation of study participants' conclusions, the convergence of multiple evidence sources such as interview transcripts, reflective field notes, and triangulation of investigators. These improved the research (Berry and Worthington, 2021; Magalhaes and Knox, 2021).

Conformity was discussed by ensuring the outcomes of the work, the product of the experiences and ideas generated from the in-depth interview rather than features and the researcher's interest. The triangulation of data also defined Conformability. The quest for anomalies in research is done by cross-checking the data with many people. In addition, conformance is assessed by external audits, which are not involved in the study process. They examined the research study's approach and evaluated the accuracy and whether the evidence confirms the observations, interpretations, and conclusions (Cherry, 2020; Renner, Schwab, and Boel-Studt, 2019; Seo, 2021).

Conformity relates to how often others affirm the outcomes. Corroborating this point emphasizes that research analysis implements objectivity (neutrality) and the control of research bias (Mohajan, 2018; Solomontos-Kountouri and Strohmeier, 2021).

Research readers have applied transferability. It does not require significant statements but allows research readers to correlate a study's elements and their own experiences. The investigator conducted some aspects of data management to resolve transferability, as indicated in the archival log. There are whole sets of interview protocols included in the archive. The transcripts and the translated versions are available on the file on request. This reference to the paper trail of the investigation enables readers and other scholars to pass the conclusion of this inquiry to other cases or replicate this analysis's procedures as closely as possible (Asha, Waasdorp, and Bradshaw, 2018; Berkowitz, 2017).

Furthermore, transferability relates to how well the results translate to other school environments and relies on the parallels between the two comparative environments. Thick explanations allow readers to make decisions about transferability and judgment. This article's detailed descriptions can enable readers to pass information to other settings and settings (Becker, Berger, Luckmann, Burawoy, Gans, Gerson, and Mills, 2019; Pekrun, 2016).

Dependability is created by following the correct procedures that should be recorded in detail so that future researchers can replicate the study. It is also accomplished by defining what was planned and performed using detailed and precise analysis design and execution. Operational specifics of data collection are also achieved. Dependability is a criterion known to be similar to reliability, and that also concerns the consistency of the results over time (Arseneault, Walsh, Trzesniewski, Newcombe, Caspi, and Moffitt, 2016; Pellegrini, 2018).

In addition, reliability is enhanced by standard qualitative techniques such as audit trails, rich documentation, triangulation, and conventional approaches using the same human instrument, such as inter-coder or inter-observer agreement and code-recode consistency. In this research method, the more consistent the researcher has been, the more trustworthy and reliable the findings are (Berkowitz, 2017; Pellegrini, 2018; Vaillancourt and Farrell, 2021).

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Considering the learners were involved in the research study, they might hesitate to reveal and withhold some data out of fear. However, as part of the rigor of analysis and resisting the temptation to pursue this report, many precautions were used to ensure that informants calculate their confidentiality and non-disclosure, wipe out their fears and create confidence and trust. Ethical values must drive research: respect for individuals, beneficence, fairness, consent, and confidentiality (Berbenishty, Astor, and Astor, 2016; Perry, Ostrov, Murray-Close, Blakely-McClure, DeJesus-Rodrigues, and Wesolowski, 2021).

Respect for individuals requires a determination to protect people from the abuse of their vulnerabilities, to ensure the autonomy of study participants, and where sovereignty may be diminished. It was necessary to seek approval from the Division Heads and Superintendents or the school where they were allocated for the data collection involved in the research before performing a study (Renner, Schwab, and Boel-Studt, 2019; Seo, 2021).

In the study, they were collected at an early stage. As a sign of my appreciation for the individuals involved in the research, I went through all these procedures. Educated and voluntary consent is a process to ensure that individuals understand what it means to engage in a specific research study to determine if they want to participate in an aware, deliberate manner. One of the most critical methods for maintaining respect for individuals during research is informed consent (Berry and Worthington, 2021; Besag, 2018).

I clarified the goals and intent of this research study orally and in writing before I performed the in-depth interviews and made it clear that the proceedings would be audio-taped. I asked them to sign a written permit after receiving their permission. The informants would also announce the findings and results of the research as I felt they had the right to know because they were the ones in the first place involved and to give them due to recognition (Knox and Dynes, 2020; Kauffman and Landrum, 2017).

Beneficence includes a commitment to reduce research-related risks, including psychological and social risks, and to maximize the benefits that research participants derive. The interviewee's anonymity concerning the information exchanged is retained to reduce the risks or damage to the participants. Participants are secured, so that information or data files are not left in notebooks or insecure computer files (Boivin, Hymel, and Bukowski, 2016; Brown, 2018).

The confidentiality of the results and the security of informants' identities were clarified by using a coding scheme to conceal their true identities. Teachers were previously told that the entire database included digital voice recorders, typed transcripts, field notes, and other related materials (Kvale, 2016; O'Moore and Kirkham, 2021).

Justice needs a commitment to ensure that the costs and benefits arising from the study are equally distributed. It is necessary to integrate a method of recognizing participants' contributions to the success of the research project into the research plan and to reimburse them for their efforts in various ways (Bradley, Doolittle, and Bartolotta, 2018; Pekrun, 2016).

In-depth interviews required extensive individual consultations to discuss their viewpoints on a specific concept, initiative, or circumstance with few respondents. We asked the participants about their perspectives, hopes, ideas, and perceptions. The success of an in-depth interview depends mainly on the interviewer's personal and professional qualities (Ma, 2017; Murray, Santos, Bertodli, Murray, Artech, and Tovo-Rodrigues, 2019).

I must also have the ability to listen carefully, digest, and appreciate responses from the participants. It is also equally critical that a researcher and interviewer have a clear and rational mind and quickly think about the main points of the participants' responses. As individuals, we need curiosity, interest, and respect for others. Each instructor was told that their memories and personal accounts would be protected, and no one would be able to access the details they gave me during the interviewing. I have separated my outlook on this and did not make personal statements during the interviews on the participants' responses (Shirley and Cornell, 2021; Tani, Greenman, Schneider, and Fregoso, 2018).

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The findings, comparisons to other studies, limits of the research, implications for future research, and overall significance of the qualitative research on verbal and physical aggression as experienced by grade 6 pupils are presented in this chapter.

The study's goal was to characterize the experiences of those who have been subjected to verbal and physical aggression. The researchers obtained the relevant information during the in-depth interview with the participants.

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The study's findings may aid school administrators and teachers in comprehending the plight of victimized elementary school students. Also, to provide necessary intervention programs to help them live in a healthy, safe, and equal environment and motivate them to improve their performance until they are able to complete their studies.

This section covered the study's findings, which were derived from interviews with pupils who had been subjected to verbal and physical aggression. Three primary themes emerged from the respondents' responses. These were experiences, impacts, and overcome and lessons.

The participants' affairs came out with the first coded structured theme, such as personal battles with three categorized themes: low self-esteem, maladjustment, and physically weaker. Another coded structured theme is the environmental factor with three organized themes: peer rejection, race, and poor or low-income family (Kauffman and Landrum, 2017; Holt, Finkelhor, and Kantor, 2017).

While the impact of verbal and physical aggression as experienced by grade 6 pupils came out the first coded structured theme: self-repercussion with two categorized themes: anxiety and depression and loneliness. The other coded structured article is community support with two organized pieces: family support and teacher support (Becker, Berger, Luckmann, Burawoy, Gans, Gerson, and Mills, 2019; Seo, 2021).

Meanwhile, participants have overcome and gained lessons from these experiences. The first coded structured theme was the emotional impact with two categorized themes: forgiveness and healing, and managing stress. At the same time, the other coded structured theme was the environmental impact with three organized themes: leaning on friends and family, helping others, and raising awareness (Abdullah, 2019; Boivin, Hymel, and Bukowski, 2016).

The participants of this study have shared the same notion and ideas regarding their verbal and physical aggression experiences. Physical aggressiveness is described as causing bodily harm to another person by hitting, beating, or using items. Verbal aggression is defined as causing mental damage to another person by using unpleasant words. As a result of being beaten and hearing unpleasant remarks like "ugly" and "inky-black," participant 1 identified herself as having a low sense of self-worth. While participant 2 reported his bullies as being more significant than him and that they often beat him up and told him he was too small to fight back, he opted to remain silent. He also stated that he tended to keep his head down and lacked confidence (Hanrock, Algozzine, and Lim, 2021; Olweus, 2017).

When participant 3 encountered a bully, he occasionally noticed his failure to respond successfully and satisfactorily to the demands of his surroundings. He felt ridiculous when the teacher called him while the bullies were present, just as he did inside the classroom. He preferred to keep his mouth shut. Participant 4, on the other hand, had negative feelings against bullies and expresses them through acts of vandalism, addiction, stealing, and physical and emotional aggressiveness (Etikan and Bala, 2017; Holt, Kaufman-Kantor, and Finkelhor, 2018).

Participant 1 described a negative encounter with physical aggression. She recalled a situation in which she was walking to the school canteen when the participant was pushed and could not do anything since, she was physically exhausted. The aggressors were described as physically strong by participant 3. The aggressors were then the ones who were victimized and were physically weak. He recalled a day when he was punched out of nowhere (Kumpulainen and Rasanen, 2020; Rigby and Slee, 2019).

Participant 2 recalled a time when he felt rejected by his classmates due to the aggressors' constant victimization of him because of his appearance. He was also occasionally left out of group events because he found it challenging to fit in. While participant 3 stated that she was mainly left out of the group and felt lonely when she was not involved (Magalhaes and Knox, 2021; Olweus, 2019).

Participant 4 knew his race (B'laan) and believed it was one of the reasons these aggressors were victimizing him. According to the study, physical and mental aggressiveness and the reasons students were harassed vary depending on contextual factors such as urbanization and race (Cherry, 2020; Lindstrom, Waasdorp, Gaias, and Bradshaw, 2019).

Participants 2 and 3 reported that they were from a low-income household and had been maltreated due to their circumstances. When they were uttered unpleasant things about their family's money, they were the most verbally victimized. Participant 3 stated that no matter how often she complained, her parents could not help her (Burke and Nishioka, 2019; O'Moore and Kirkham, 2021).

They all arrived at the same conclusion on the effects of verbal and physical hostility, wherein participant 1's life was impacted due to being a victim of verbal and physical aggression. She is unhappy, depressed, and worried much of the time. She has recalled her experiences of being intimidated at school and being warned to be vigilant at the school gate. While participant 2 stated that he disliked dealing with aggressors. He was afraid he would be punched or maybe thrown off his feet. He also mentioned a time in class when someone verbally teased him, and he expressed some displeasure before being pounded, and he felt anxious the rest of the time due to the incident. While participant 3 was unable to stop worrying or believed that if she did, horrible things would occur (Berkowitz, 2017; Renner, Schwab, and Boel-Studt, 2019).

Participants sensed their families' support. Even though they were not wealthy, participant 2 stated that he had never felt unloved by his family, but rather that they loved and supported him. While participant 4 expressed his grief at school due to bullying, he felt the affection of his father and mother and his siblings at home. He appreciated the help he received (Babinski and McQuade, 2019; Poling, Smith, Taylor, and Worth, 2019).

Additionally, participants have agreed to enlist the help of a few teachers. Inside the classroom, participant 1 described her experience that anytime she felt unsafe or someone threatened her, she usually ignored it; but, if she felt truly in danger, she sought out a teacher, particularly her adviser, and by then, she felt safe. When participant 3 felt terrified of the aggressors, she would approach her teacher, and the aggressor would no longer victimize her (Besag, 2018; Swit, McMaugh, and Warburton, 2018).

Meanwhile, participants have discussed the importance of forgiveness, particularly when it came to their aggressors. Participant 1 previously stated that she found it difficult to forgive, but she has since recognized that these aggressors merely required attention that they did not receive at home. As a result, participant 1 was willing to forgive them. Participant 4 has stated that he held no grudges against his aggressors. He forgave them because he felt sorry for them, and their actions no longer harm him. He also felt healed because he was no longer enraged by the aggressors (Bielova, 2018; Solomontos-Kountouri and Strohmeier, 2021).

They have placed a strong emphasis on stress management. Participants could handle their tension better because they discussed the importance of forgiveness and how they had forgiven their aggressors. They were a little more concerned than before. Participant 2 was more concerned with his well-being than other issues. Since she had forgiven her aggressor, participant 3 felt psychologically and physically healthy. She then had the impression that she could control her tension. She went on to say that happiness is crucial in life (Cohen, 20016; Vaillancourt and Farrell, 2021).

As a result of her family and friends, participant 1 has become more forgiving. She has been more understanding of the situation due to her family and friends, and she knows she could always rely on them whenever she was upset by the aggressors. While participant 3 described how her father and mother reminded her that they were always there for her if she had an issue at school and that she could trust them. She also mentioned her parents adored her (Duke and Norton, 2017; Worth, Smith, and Poling, 2021).

Participants 3 and 4 have agreed that schoolchildren should be informed more. And that the teachers are genuine about instilling these values in their students. Teacher training and participation in workshops positively impacted teachers' awareness of indirect aggression (verbally and physically) and their ability to intervene. In summary, the goal of this study was to evaluate a brief program targeted at raising awareness of verbal and physical aggression and victimization among teachers, students, and their parents in grades 4–6 (Asha, Waasdorp, and Bradshaw, 2018; Firestone, 2019).

It is widely acknowledged that children who have been victims of aggression have low self-esteem. However, the research is mixed when it comes to youngsters who bullied. Passive bullies may be worried and insecure. He believed that youngsters who engaged in physical and mental aggressiveness did not have low self-esteem. Bullying others was not linked to low self-esteem, but a child victimized by physical and psychological aggression experienced low self-esteem. Additionally, significant characteristics of victims of the attack include low self-esteem and high social anxiety (Ma, 2017; O'Moore, and Kirkham, 2017).

Furthermore, the explanatory model for bullying involvement demonstrated the association with maladjustment. The global level of social skills only indirectly predicted aggression and victimization. Bullying involvement could be partly explained by differences in sociometric popularity resulting from the degree of confusion determined by the child's level of social skills (Arseneault, Walsh, Trzesniewski, Newcombe, Caspi, and Moffitt, 2016; Holt and Espelage, 2017).

Moreover, in response to criticism that bullying has traditionally been described as physical harassment, academics increasingly consider bullying a form of violence. One learner or a group of learners harassed a victim verbally or physically without provocation. Bullies are known for their aggressive behavior and frequently use their physical strength to their advantage, and the victims consider themselves physically weak. Additionally, the learners who harassed others needed to feel powerful and in command. They seem to get pleasure from inflicting pain and suffering on others, showed no empathy for their victims, and frequently justify their actions by claiming that their victims provoked them in some way (Banks, 2017; Tremblay, Nagin, Seguin, Zoccolillo, Zelazo, Boivin, and Japel, 2019).

In addition, ejection and discrimination mediated the association between social withdrawal and loneliness, whereas peer victimization mediated the link between peer rejection and loneliness. This was according to mediation tests. Social withdrawal, peer rejection, peer discrimination, and loneliness were all significant predictors of depressed mood, and a child's subjective feeling of loneliness mediated the association between discrimination and depression. Interpersonal factors such as peer rejection predicted increases in victimization among elementary school children over a year (Dill, Vernberg, Fonagy, Twemlow, and Gamm, 2018; Ma, 2017).

According to the study, physical and mental violence involvement and why pupils were bullied vary depending on contextual factors such as urbanization and race. Additionally, African American youth are more likely to be bullied because of their clothing and physical appearance. They are likely to perceive the peer climate as supportive of aggressive behaviors, less likely to seek help from adults when bullied, and more likely to experience depression due to being forced (Lindstrom, Waasdorp, Gaias, and Bradshaw, 2019; Firestone, 2019).

Furthermore, working time may reduce parents' ability to dedicate time and energy to their children, compromising their ability to cultivate, retain, and invest social capital in their socialization. Long work hours for low pay, uncertain employment, and other associated disadvantages (e.g., failing local schools) may impede healthy social capital investments in children's outcomes in disadvantaged or low-income families. As with victims of aggression, children from low-income families are more likely to be bullied (Craig and Pepler, 2019; Pellegrini, 2018).

On the other hand, compared to the aggressor or non-involved children, being a victim of physical and verbal aggression is related to more internalizing difficulties and peer relational problems. Aggression victims experience reduced self-esteem and greater levels of depression and anxiety (Bielova, 2018; Cohen, 2016).

Somehow, having few friends, having friends who cannot aid or defend you, and being rejected by your peer group are the three critical social risk factors for victimization. Victims and bullies are over-represented in the sociometric 'rejected' category (that is, they receive many 'like least' and few 'like most' nominations from classmates), according to research in the United States and England (Cherry, 2020; Espelage, Low, Polanin, and Brown, 2018).

Moreover, the families of victims have a distinct set of features. Families of victims frequently show high degrees of togetherness in this scenario. Furthermore, victims are more likely to have less authoritative parents and live in homes with low levels of negotiation and high levels of conflict. According to some data, family structure and money are linked to peer victimization (Burke and Nishioka, 2019; Holt, Kaufman-Kantor, and Finkelhor, 2018; Firestone, 2019).

Thus, teachers may assume they frequently intervene in bullying situations; however, observational research conducted in Canada found that teachers intervene in just 15% to 18% of bullying occurrences in the classroom and on the playground. When bullying occurs in the school, teachers are more aware of it. In an unstructured, free-range, weakly supervised garden, however, the likelihood of adult intervention in bullying interactions may be lower. Furthermore, teachers are not always aware of bullying (Berkowitz, 2017; Pellegrini, 2018).

It is crucial to investigate how children view teachers' responses to bullying at school for various reasons. To begin with, school personnel's impressions of violence at their school may not be accurate. For example, a recent study in the United States discovered that adults in the school community (school workers) often consider bullying and social violence are 'mild' to 'moderately severe' issues. In contrast, children regularly identify it as a 'severe' issue. As a result, polling learners—who are aware of violence in their school even if they are not physically present when it occurs—might be a more trustworthy source of information for teachers (Cohen, 2016; Darke, Shanks, and Broadbent, 2018).

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Second, research on school climate has shown the impact of staff responses to violent occurrences in influencing student sentiments of safety and fear of violence at school. As a result, learners' views of their teachers' reactions to violence are potent markers of their opinions of security and dread at school (Benbenishty, Astor, and Astor, 2016; Ma, 2017).

Forgiveness is defined as a method of coping used in the face of aggressiveness, betrayals, and other forms of wrongdoing. An individual who has been the victim of aggression is prone to have an adverse emotional reaction known as unforgiveness, especially if they meditate on the violence. Additionally, the term "forgiveness" is frequently used in the literature to refer to interpersonal forgiveness, in which one person forgives another (Egan, 2019; Holt and Espelage, 2017).

Furthermore, forgiveness and physical health are higher levels of both traits, and state forgiveness foresees healthier cardiovascular reactivity among the learners during and following relived interpersonal aggression. Additionally, those with higher state forgiveness also reported fewer symptoms of physical illness. The trait of forgiveness predicts lower stress levels and better self-reported health. Further, the study suggested that school learners should be assisted to be forgiving to increase their state forgiveness in response to being victimized. They might enjoy superior health status and be protected against some detrimental effects of not being forgiven (Egan, 2019; Vaillancourt and Farrell, 2021).

According to research, youth could obtain social support from various sources, resulting in positive outcomes. Youth's primary source of social support frequently fluctuates with their age. Youths seek assistance mainly from their parents when they are young, but peer support becomes increasingly important as they enter adolescence. Furthermore, older adolescents report receiving less support from all sources than younger adolescents. However, both kinds of support are vital to evaluate, given that kids say accepting different social provisions from parents than from peers (Duke and Norton, 2017; Holt and Espelage, 2017).

In addition, perhaps youngsters with a high level of Extraversion and Agreeability would be more well-known. Because they are not frightened of losing status in social circumstances, including bullying, they are more likely to help others than their less Extroverted or Agreeable counterparts. The children who come to the help of their victims would also be considered heroes. Warmth and Tender-mindedness are prevalent in the Extroverted, Agreeable personality type. Conscientiousness has a personality feature that entails regard for others. Defenders of Bully Victims are known for their sense of order, regulations, and duty. While, aggressive victims would have the minor emotional instability and the highest energy levels, openness, friendliness, and conscientiousness among all the children in the sample (Pellegrini, 2018; Renner, Schwab, Boel-Studt, 2019).

Additionally, teacher training and participation in workshops had a good effect on increasing teachers' awareness of indirect aggression (verbally and physically) and their ability to act preventively on the problem. To summarize, the purpose of this study was to assess a brief program aimed at boosting awareness of verbal and physical forcefulness and discrimination among instructors and pupils in Grades 4–6, as well as their parents (Tani, Greenman, Schneider, and Fregosso, 2018; Vaillancourt and Farrell, 2021).

The study included four (4) grade six (6) pupils who had been subjected to verbal and physical aggression. These individuals were chosen using the criteria outlined in this study. The number of participants was based on Creswell's (2016) view that the number of participants in a qualitative study range from 4 to 25. Furthermore, this research was limited to the perspectives of grade 6 pupils who have been subjected to verbal and physical aggression.

The study's findings were limited to the experiences of grade 6 students who had been subjected to verbal and physical aggression. Another study of this type could be done in other municipalities or divisions to confirm the findings of this one.

Furthermore, more study may be done to re-interview some of the individuals to see if their experiences, life consequences, and lessons gained and overcome as grade 6 students who have been subjected to verbal and physical aggression have changed over time.

Another study might be undertaken from the perspective of aggressor learners to gather more information and better grasp what it means to be verbally and physically violent.

The Department of Education's most primary students were the victims of verbal and physical abuse. As an outcome, I believed that the study is vital to understand better the learners who have been victimized, their experiences, the repercussions on their lives, how they overcome it, and the lesson they learn from it. As a result, it promotes social equality

and encourages learners to complete their studies. It can be utilized as a resource for other teachers working with learners on the verge of dropping out, as a source of patience and compassion. School administrators and teachers need to know the sentiments of children victimized by verbal and physical aggression at school to provide intervention or assistance to keep them in school and find joy in learning. This research is also a great help in educating society on how to handle the situation and at least minimize the verbal and physical aggressiveness situation. It is a better reference for school administrators to provide follow-up and intervention to learners at risk of dropping out because they are being bullied (Egan, 2019; Holt and Espelage, 2017).

The school administrators and teachers must be aware of the feelings of students who have been subjected to verbal and physical aggression at school to intervene or provide aid to keep the learners in school and enjoy studying. This study would also aid in educating society on how to manage situations and, at the very least, reduce verbal and physical aggression. It is a better resource for school officials to follow up and intervene with learners at risk of dropping out due to verbal and physical attacks (Burke and Nishioka, 2019; Holt, Kaufman-Kantor, and Finkelhor, 2018; Firestone, 2019).

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